

On the Large Eddy Simulation of Large Eddy Breakup Unit Over a Flat Plate

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Abstract

Employing Large Eddy Breakup Units (LEBUs) is a common and traditional technique in the context of flow control to diminish skin friction drag and noise. These devices disrupt the flow, altering the turbulence structure and reducing the energy in large-scale turbulent eddies, thereby lowering skin friction drag. In this research, two different configurations of single and double units over a flat plate are investigated, and reductions in skin friction and pressure fluctuations are observed compared to the baseline of no LEBU in the flow domain. The type of LEBUs used is the flat plate type. The investigation has been performed using Fluent commercial software and Large Eddy Simulation (LES).

Keywords: *Large Eddy Breakup Unit (LEBU) – Large Eddy Simulation (LES) – Turbulent Boundary Layer (TBL) – CFD – Flow Control*

1. Introduction

The Large-Eddy Break-Up (LEBU) devices have been extensively studied for their potential to reduce skin friction drag in turbulent boundary layers. These devices disrupt large-scale turbulent structures, modifying turbulence characteristics and reducing skin friction. While early studies showed promising results, the overall net drag reduction remains debated due to the drag induced by the LEBU devices themselves. This introduction reviews key studies on LEBUs, highlighting their methodologies, governing physics, and results, followed by the focus of the current study.

Chin et al., [1] studied a Large-Eddy-Break-up Device (LEBU) in a moderate Reynolds number turbulent boundary layer using high-resolution LES. The research aimed to analyze LEBU effects on skin friction and drag, employing an immersed boundary method. Results showed a 12% local skin friction reduction but no net drag reduction due to device drag. The study highlighted turbulence modification, with reduced large-scale energy and increased small-scale

energy downstream of the LEBU. Also, Chin et al., [2] examined LEBU effects on the turbulent/non-turbulent interface (TNTI) using well-resolved LES. The study focused on boundary layer growth and turbulence modulation, showing a 12% skin friction reduction and narrower turbulent structures downstream. The LEBU attenuated TNTI fluctuations and delayed boundary layer growth by breaking up large eddies. Spalart et al., [3] used DNS to study LEBUs for aerodynamic noise reduction by weakening wall pressure fluctuations. The study employed a multi-block implicit numerical method, revealing reduced pressure fluctuations over a short distance (6 boundary layer thicknesses). Co-rotating vortex generators, however, intensified pressure fluctuations, contrary to expectations. Anders, [4] explored airfoil-shaped LEBUs for turbulent drag reduction in aircraft applications. Wind tunnel experiments demonstrated up to 30% local skin friction reduction and 7% net drag reduction. Airfoil-shaped LEBUs showed superior structural integrity and performance compared to flat plates. Chan et al., [5] analyzed skin friction reduction using the FIK identity and quadrant analysis in DNS and LES. The study decomposed skin friction into large-scale and small-scale contributions, showing the LEBU modified ejection and sweep events to reduce skin friction. Alfredsson et al., [6] reviewed LEBU effectiveness over four decades, concluding no net drag reduction when accounting for device drag. The study suggested alternative applications, such as reducing optical distortions or wall pressure fluctuations, and highlighted discrepancies in earlier findings. Chong et al., [7] investigated LEBU effects on wall pressure fluctuations for noise mitigation. Wind tunnel experiments with a NACA0014 airfoil LEBU showed reduced pressure fluctuations when placed more than three boundary layer thicknesses upstream, altering turbulent spot structure and pressure spectra.

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This study focuses on reducing skin friction drag using LEBU devices, emphasizing the underlying mechanisms through high-resolution numerical simulations. The research employs large eddy simulation (LES) in Fluent commercial software to provide insights into the interaction between LEBUs and turbulent boundary layers. The innovation of this study lies in implementing LEBUs in the numerical setup using a novel method, avoiding interruptions and reinitialization in the solution. Additionally, two different configurations are investigated and compared with a baseline turbulent boundary layer. By analyzing the effects of LEBUs on turbulence statistics and skin friction, this study aims to contribute to optimizing LEBU designs for practical drag reduction applications.

2. Material and Method

2.1. Problem Description

Reducing the skin friction drag in the aerodynamics has a high degree of importance. To generalize the problem and results, the Skin Friction Coefficient (C_f) and Pressure Fluctuations were selected for investigation.

2.2. Governing Equations

Continuity Equation (Incompressible) [8], (1):

$$1) \quad \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0$$

Momentum Equation (2):

$$2) \quad \frac{D\mathbf{u}}{Dt} = -\nabla p + \nu \nabla^2 \mathbf{u} + \mathbf{f}$$

where:

$D\mathbf{u}/Dt$ is the material derivative of the velocity field \mathbf{u} , defined as $\partial\mathbf{u}/\partial t + (\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{u}$. ∇p is the gradient of the pressure field. ν is the kinematic viscosity. $\nabla^2 \mathbf{u}$ is the Laplacian of the velocity field. \mathbf{f} represents external forces acting on the fluid.

In the context of Large Eddy Simulation (LES), the filtered Navier-Stokes equations are used, and the subgrid-scale stress tensor τ_{ij} is introduced to account for the effects of the unresolved scales, Eq. (3):

$$3) \quad \frac{D\bar{\mathbf{u}}}{Dt} = -\nabla \bar{p} + \nu \nabla^2 \bar{\mathbf{u}} - \nabla \cdot \tau_{ij} + \bar{\mathbf{f}}$$

where:

$\bar{\mathbf{u}}$ is the filtered velocity field. \bar{p} is the filtered pressure field. τ_{ij} is the subgrid-scale stress tensor.

3. Numerical Setup

In this section, the numerical procedure, including domain, grid, and methodology, is elaborated in detail. The computational infrastructure used in this study is a Windows-based Fluent 24.0, utilizing 16 CPU cores of AMD R9-5950X for the main LES simulations, in addition to an RTX 3060 Titan GPU used for initial RANS and URANS simulations, leveraging NVIDIA's CUDA technology. The simulation started with RANS, then URANS, and subsequently switched to LES. The time step of 5E-5, y^+ of less than 1, and Courant Friedrichs Lewy (CFL) number of around 1 were checked in URANS. Implementing the simulation step by step like this not only guarantees convergence but also helps to diagnose and troubleshoot errors.

For the computational domain, a 3D flat plate is selected with dimensions of 30mm(W) \times 30mm(H) \times 1000mm(L). The boundary conditions are shown in Figure 1 and listed in Table 1. To create a turbulent boundary condition in a logical length of the flat plate in LES, a Synthetic Turbulence Generator (STG) was employed at the inlet. The STG was set to not have any search scale limiter. Additionally, a turbulent intensity of 10% with a turbulent length scale of 2mm was used at the inlet. These values were obtained using trial and error to create controlled turbulence over the flat plate, which is suitable to be managed by means of LEBUs. Furthermore, a Blasius Profile was enforced at the inlet using a compiled type User Defined Function (UDF).

A Transient Pressure-Based solver type, along with Absolute velocity formulation, without considering the effect of Gravity body force, was used in this simulation. In RANS and URANS, the Shear Stress Transport (SST) version of K-Omega was used, and the results were interpolated to be the initial values for LES.

In LES, the Subgrid-Scale model selected for this simulation is the Wall-Adapting Local Eddy-Viscosity (WALE) model. The WALE model is designed to return the correct wall asymptotic (y^3) behavior for wall-bounded flows. Another advantage of the WALE model is that it returns zero turbulent viscosity for laminar shear flows. This allows for the correct treatment of laminar zones in the domain.

Figure1. Domain and the boundary conditions

Table 1. Boundary conditions

Name / Features	Boundary Type	Velocity and Direction
Inlet	Velocity Inlet	7.5 m/s, \hat{i} + Perturbation
Outlet	Pressure Outlet	None
Wall	Wall	No-Slip
Periodic-Positive	Periodic - Translational	0m/s, Spanwise, \hat{k}
Periodic-Negative	Periodic - Translational	0m/s, Spanwise, \hat{k}
Symmetry	Symmetry	None

In contrast, the Smagorinsky-Lilly model, for example, produces nonzero turbulent viscosity. The WALE model is therefore preferable compared to the Smagorinsky-Lilly model. Furthermore, for the Near-Wall Treatment, the Kader Blending model was used. In this model, when the mesh is fine enough to resolve the laminar sublayer, the wall shear stress is obtained from the laminar stress-strain relationship. If the mesh is too coarse to resolve the laminar sublayer, it is assumed that the centroid of the wall-adjacent cell falls within the logarithmic region of the boundary layer, and the law-of-the-wall is employed. If the mesh is such that the first near-wall point is within the buffer region, then the two above laws are blended.

To solve equations, the SIMPLE algorithm was utilized for pressure-velocity coupling. For the spatial discretization, the Least Squares Cell-Based model, Second Order, and Bounded Central Differencing were selected for Gradient, Pressure, and Momentum, respectively. Also, for the Transient Formulation, the

Bounded Second Order Implicit model was employed. As structured cells were used in this simulation, the Warped-Face Gradient Correction was applied.

3.1. Numerical Procedure and Grid Generation

Since a Finite Volume Method (FVM) has been utilized for this simulation, domain discretization was necessary. Therefore, a structured mesh was used to discretize the computational domain. Grid generation started with dividing the domain into 1mm cells with a bias toward the wall, resulting in about 1 million cells. Then, refinement was applied to the near-wall region to ensure the y^+ was kept less than 1, with an average of 0.14, which perfectly captures the boundary layer. This resulted in 2 million cells, using Manual Mesh Refinement (MMR). Next, the thickness of the inner layer and outer layer was calculated based on an average friction velocity of 0.394 m/s from relations (4, 5) below:

$$(4,5) \quad u_\tau = \sqrt{\frac{\tau_w}{\rho}}, \quad y = \frac{y^+ \nu}{u_\tau}$$

The obtained amounts are: $y = 1.13\text{mm}$ for the inner layer ($y^+ = 30$) and $y = 5.63\text{mm}$ for the outer layer ($y^+ = 150$).

Figure 2. Grid of TBL case, zoomed to show near wall refined cells

Then, based on these amounts and a safety factor, the cells up to a height of 7mm were refined by MMR, resulting in a 4.8M mesh. With this grid size, the

solution of the Turbulent Boundary Layer (TBL) was obtained, which serves as the baseline. The grid is represented in Figure 2.

Figure 3. Mesh refinement method for an acceptable LES [9]

The policy of this kind of mesh refinement is in agreement with Ansys documents. Generally, for the RANS and URANS simulations, there are high Aspect Ratio (AR) cells near the wall, just to achieve acceptable y^+ . In contrast, in LES, it must be considered that the AR must be preserved near unity. In Figure 3, there is an example of fine mesh for LES, according to Ansys resources. From Figure 3, the refinement must take place step by step from the free stream region to the outer layer, then the inner layer, and finally the near-wall area. It should be noted that the cell sizes and refinements have been carried out in a way that at least an area of 4 by 4 cells in the outer layer can cover a circular turbulent structure with a

length scale (diameter) of 2mm. In lower layers, this amount increased with refinements. For the wake region of LEBUs, this covering area is at least an 8 by 8 cell region. This guarantees that the turbulent structures are well captured. The next step was to add the LEBUs. First, a single configuration was tested, followed by a dual configuration. An innovative method was used to add devices to the computational domain to save computational costs. Instead of designing a new CAD model and starting the simulation from zero time, the devices were added and solved relative to the TBL case. The first location of the device was selected to be at 500mm length of the channel (halfway),

Figure 4. Single and double configurations mesh and their y^+ per flow time in seconds

which allows the flow to develop downstream, and at 3mm height ($y^+ = 80$), which is in the outer layer and allows the device to eliminate large structures or break them down into small-sized eddies.

Second, based on the location of the device and boundary layer thickness at that location, the geometrical features of the LEBU were calculated to be 0.02δ thickness, 1δ length, and the width of the channel. The amount of δ at the LEBU location was around 6mm. Next, to implement this new method, a

region with an offset of 2mm was selected in the grid, and 2 levels of MMR were applied to that region to allow for the selection of a precise location for the unit among the cells with the desired thickness. After selecting cells that were precisely at the location of the LEBU, instead of patching them with zero velocity, which is not a rational way, that zone was separated from the domain and then removed from the computational domain. The remaining interface at that location was set to be a no-slip wall. With this method,

we successfully added the LEBU instantly in the domain and resumed the solution without any kind of initialization. The only requirement is to keep the y^+ of the device less than 1.

As the mesh was fine enough, at the moment of adding the device, the maximum y^+ was 2. Then, 3 levels of MMR were applied to the wall of the unit in all directions, keeping the average y^+ around 0.43, with an addition of 1 million cells per unit (final grid size for single unit configuration was 5.8 million cells and for double unit configuration 6.8 million cells). It should be noted that the wake region of the devices took 1 level of MMR to preserve the generated wake. The grids of single and double configurations, in addition to their y^+ graphs, are represented in Figure 4.

4. Results and Discussion

The effect of adding LEBU is discussed here. Based on the literature review, it is expected to reduce the skin friction coefficient (C_f), damp pressure fluctuations, and break large structures into smaller ones. Figure 5 shows pressure coefficient (C_p) variations along the X direction, streamwise, for the three cases of TBL, single unit, and double unit configurations, on different lines spaced in the spanwise direction.

In all cases, the value of C_p starts from a high value, which is a laminar effect, and settles to approximately unit values where the changes occur. At the leading edge of the flat plate, the flow is typically laminar, and the pressure is relatively high due to the stagnation effect. This results in a high C_p value at the start of the plate. As the flow transitions to a turbulent boundary layer, the pressure drops, and C_p decreases. In the TBL case, C_p settles around 7 and varies to around 0 along the X direction, while in the two other cases with LEBU, the C_p starts from 10 and reduces to 0. The presence of LEBU units alters the pressure distribution within the boundary layer. The units disrupt the flow, causing local changes in pressure. This is reflected in the C_p distribution along the streamwise direction.

Furthermore, the LEBUs are located at 0.5m and 0.6m, and their effect on C_p changes can be observed in the graphs. Where the units are located, a sudden reduction occurs in C_p . In the single unit case, the flow reattaches and C_p recovers after the drop. However, the second unit causes a further reduction in C_p , leading to a step-like decrease. The flow does not fully recover

between the two units, resulting in a cumulative effect on the pressure distribution. The C_f is reported in same format in Figure 6.

Figure 5. Pressure coefficient spatial variations in streamwise direction on the flat plate

The C_f did not change considerably in the average amounts. The area-weighted average of C_f for the TBL case is 0.274, for the single unit case is 0.273, and for the double unit case is 0.271. However, looking more precisely, it shows that the peak values in the double unit case have decreased. Also, in the downstream of the LEBU, where is the region of influence, the C_f has decreased significantly. Eventually, with more precise placement, geometry, and configuration of LEBUs, more effective performance can be achieved in C_f reduction.

Regarding the pressure fluctuations over the flat plate, shown in Figure 7, it can be observed that the pressure fluctuations decreased significantly with the addition of LEBU to the flow passing over the flat plate. This matches the findings of PR Spalart et al. (2006), PH Alfredsson and R Orlu (2018), and TP Chong et al. (2024). Taking a closer look at the

structure breakup visually in Figure 8, it is observed that the breakup occurs in large structures after encountering the LEBU, as expected. The figure is constructed from animation frames, recorded with 15 frame per second (FPS). The large structure is illustrated with a dashed circle, which continues and breaks up in collision with LEBU, and in last frame the structure is fully broken to small ones.

Figure 6. Skin friction coefficient variations in streamwise direction on the flat plate

After breakup, the structures move from the top and bottom sides of the LEBU. A portion of these structures collides with the wall, while another portion goes through the outer layer, attaches to the free stream, and is eliminated due to the high momentum of the free stream. However, in this collision, a small portion of the structure moves with the wake of the LEBU toward downstream. Additionally, Figure 8 shows that the second LEBU eliminates the third portion of the remnant coherent structure, which moved downstream with the wake of the LEBU.

It shows that some of the broken structures, after facing the wall, augment the near-wall structures and rise to the outer layer. These risen structures then collide with the second LEBU.

Figure 7. Pressure fluctuations temporal variations in streamwise direction on the flat plate

This secondary collision can be due to the three-dimensional nature of flow instabilities and vortical structures in the near-wall region. It is evident that a two-dimensional analysis cannot present all occurring phenomena because it omits these flow events. Based on this observation, the LEBU devices can be placed in the flow not only horizontally and parallel to the flat plate but also vertically in the flow.

Moreover, from Figure 9, it is evident that the LEBUs, illustrated with white dashed-lines, can only affect and disturb those vortical structures which are passing through the altitude of their installation. Additionally, the large structures coming from upstream are broken into smaller ones, followed by a reduction in velocity magnitude due to collision and an increase in mixing locally in the wake region.

Figure 8. Animation frames of velocity contour, for the double LEBU case, showing secondary collision of coherent structure with the LEBU and breakup procedure

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, using LEBU devices in aerodynamics is a conventional way of enhancing performance by reducing skin friction drag, pressure fluctuations, and noise. In this report, a brief study on two different configurations of placing LEBUs has been conducted. First, a single unit case and then a double unit in tandem in the streamwise direction. The research purposes are satisfied, and a reduction in skin friction and pressure fluctuation has been observed. Studying

noise was not the purpose of this study. It is also concluded that different configurations, such as placing LEBUs over each other, can be more practical for eliminating different structures at higher and lower levels in the outer layer. Moreover, a vertical arrangement could perform well. Due to a lack of computational resources and time, studying different geometries was not possible. In future works, they will be investigated.

Figure 9. Iso surfaces of double unit case for three different level of vorticity, plotted by non-dimensional velocity, from top image showing high vorticity to bottom image showing low vorticity level, representing breakup procedure by LEBUs

6. References

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